
CHIANTI

An Astrophysical Database for Emission Line Spectroscopy

CHIANTI TECHNICAL REPORT No. 11

Free-free emission

1 Overview

A free electron can be deflected when interacting with an ion, giving up some kinetic energy as radiation. For an ensemble of particles the resulting emission forms a continuum, and is referred to as free-free emission, or *bremsstrahlung*.

2 Formula

The free-free emissivity for scattering from an ion X^{Z+} is

$$p_{\text{ff},\lambda}(T) = 5.444 \times 10^{-39} \epsilon(X) F(T) Z^2 \frac{e^{-u}}{T^{1/2}} \frac{c}{\lambda^2} g_{\text{ff}}(T, u) \quad \text{erg cm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ sr}^{-1} \text{ \AA}^{-1} \quad (1)$$

where ϵ is the abundance of the element relative to hydrogen, g_{ff} is free-free Gaunt factor, T is the temperature, $F(T)$ is the ionization fraction of the ion, c is the speed of light, λ is the wavelength, and u is given by

$$u = \frac{hc}{\lambda kT} \quad (2)$$

where h is Planck's constant, and k is Boltzmann's constant. For the origin of this expression please refer to Sect. 5.2 of Rybicki & Lightman (1979) or Sect. 4.7.1 of Phillips et al. (2008). Also compare to Eq. 15 of Sutherland (1998), although note that the units should be per steradian since the numerical constant is a factor 4π smaller than the one of Rybicki & Lightman (1979).

To get the total emissivity, we sum over all charged ions for elements up to zinc:

$$P_{\text{ff},\lambda}(T) = \sum_{X=1}^{X=30} \sum_{Z=1}^{Z=X} p_{\text{ff},\lambda}(T) \quad (3)$$

This is the quantity returned by the CHIANTI routine `freefree.pro`, although it is multiplied by a factor 10^{40} .

Note that the Gaunt factor is a dimensionless quantity that is generally close to unity. It is derived assuming a Maxwellian distribution of electron energies, thus the free-free emissivity cannot be used for non-Maxwellian plasmas.

3 Calling sequence (IDL)

The free-free emission is calculated with

```
IDL> freefree, t, wvl, rad
```

where `t` is the input temperature, `wvl` an array of wavelengths, and `rad` is the output. The units of the output are $10^{-40} \text{ erg cm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ sr}^{-1} \text{ \AA}^{-1}$.

To obtain the specific intensity for an isothermal plasma, you would multiply `rad` by the emission measure—see CHIANTI Technical Report No. 3 for more details. The keyword `em_int` is available to directly input the emission measure to `freefree`.

4 Data sources

The CHIANTI free-free emission is computed using the Gaunt factors tabulated by Itoh et al. (2000) and Sutherland (1998). The former uses a relativistic approximation, but the Gaunt factor is not tabulated for the full range of temperatures needed for CHIANTI. Therefore the non-relativistic Gaunt factors of Sutherland (1998) are used to complete the CHIANTI temperature coverage.

The routine `freefree.pro` calls out to `itoh.pro` and `sutherland.pro`, and these two routines take the same keyword parameters as `freefree` (indeed they can be called as standalone routines).

4.1 Itoh data

The table containing the Itoh et al. (2000) Gaunt factors is stored in the CHIANTI `dbase/continuum` directory as `itoh.dat`. It is read directly by the routine `itoh.pro`.

4.2 Sutherland data

Sutherland (1998) provided two data files called `gffgu.dat` and `gffint.dat` that are stored in the CHIANTI `dbase/continuum` directory. The first tabulates the Gaunt factor from Eq. 15 of Sutherland (1998). The second tabulates the frequency-averaged Gaunt factor $\langle g_{\text{ff}}(\gamma^2) \rangle$ from Eq. 17. The two files are read with the IDL routines `read_gffgu.pro` and `read_gffint.pro`. The “gffgu” Gaunt factor is used by `sutherland.pro`.

References

- Itoh, N., Sakamoto, T., Kusano, S., Nozawa, S., & Kohyama, Y. 2000, *ApJS*, 128, 125, doi: <http://doi.org/10.1086/31337510.1086/313375>
- Phillips, K. J. H., Feldman, U., & Landi, E. 2008, *Ultraviolet and X-ray Spectroscopy of the Solar Atmosphere* (Cambridge University Press)
- Rybicki, G. B., & Lightman, A. P. 1979, *Radiative processes in astrophysics*
- Sutherland, R. S. 1998, *MNRAS*, 300, 321, doi: <http://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-8711.1998.01687.x10.1046/j.1365-8711.1998.01687.x>

A Document history

Ver. 1.0, 26-Apr-2019. Initial release version.